

Solutions of lead, mercury and silver were obtained from E. Merck's samples and standardized by gravimetric methods⁶. All other reagents used were of AnalaR varieties. Phosphorus pentasulphide solution was prepared by dissolving weighed quantity of the reagent in dil. NH_4OH and standardized either with sodium hypobromite amperometrically at an applied potential +0.1V (vs SCE) using rotating platinum micro-electrode or with sodium hypiodite volumetrically in an alkaline medium. Ammoniacal solution of the reagent is stable for 24 hr. The reagent should be freshly prepared daily and standardized before use.

Titrations were carried out in Fisher Electrode in conjunction with SCE and dropping mercury electrode. pH measurements were made with a line operated Beckman Zeromatic pH meter.

Procedure—Preliminary observations showed that lead, mercury and silver can be estimated quantitatively in a medium consisting of ammonium tartrate and potassium nitrate (overall concentration 0.05-0.25M) within the pH range of 7.5 to 9.5. In the actual procedure, an aliquot of lead solution was taken in a pyrex beaker containing 20 ml of 0.1M buffer and pH of the solution was adjusted to 8.5 by adding aq. ammonia. A potential of -0.2V (vs SCE) was applied and galvanometer reading was noted initially and after each addition of the titrant. After complete precipitation of lead, excess reagent gave the anodic diffusion current of its own resulting in a regular rise in the current. The plot of the volume of the reagent galvanometer reading is shown in Fig. 1 (Curve A).

Fig. 1 : Typical Amperometric Titration Curves

Estimation of lead and mercury in a binary mixture :

The titrations were carried out at an applied potential of -0.2V (vs SCE). An aliquot of a solution containing lead and mercury was taken in a pyrex beaker containing the above buffer (0.1M) and the pH of the medium

was adjusted to 8.0 with ammonia. The diffusion current was noted initially. As the addition of the reagent continued, the diffusion current of mercury reduced gradually and became steady. This intersection (Fig. 1, curve B) gave the end-point for mercury. With further addition of the titrant lead started getting precipitated and when whole of lead was removed excess of the reagent gave the anodic diffusion current of its own. The intersection at this point gave the end-point for lead.

Estimation of lead and silver : The procedure adopted in this determination was identical to that mentioned above.

Results obtained under these conditions showed that 0.4 to 5.0 mg of lead, mercury and silver can be determined accurately. It may be pointed out that the procedure is simple and easily adoptable.

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Estimation of Fly Ash Content in Portland Fly Ash Cement

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THE presence of fly ash in cement can be detected by (i) change in colour when a sample of the cement is heated at 800° or higher and (ii) floating of fly ash particles at the surface when a small quantity of the cement is shaken in water and kept undisturbed for a few minutes. While these tests can be usefully employed for checking adulteration of normal portland cement with fly ash, their application to known portland fly ash cement (pfc) is pointless. In pfc a quantitative estimation of fly ash content is needed. A method involving extraction of pozzolana cement with a solution of picric acid in methyl alcohol leaving a residue of

undissolved pozzolana has been reported by Lea⁽¹⁾. The pozzolanas mentioned are natural pozzolanas and burnt kaolin. The applicability of this method for quantitative estimation of fly ash content in pfc was examined.

Samples of pfc having fly ash content ranging from 5 to 30 per cent by weight were prepared in the laboratory by intimately mixing weighed quantities of portland cement and fly ash. 0.5 g of each of the samples was stirred with 5 g picric acid and 30 ml methyl alcohol for 10 mins. After adding 20 ml distilled water, stirring was continued for 30 mins. It was then filtered and the residue washed with methyl alcohol, followed by warm water, dried and ignited at 1000°. The fly ash content was calculated from the weight of the ignited residue. The results obtained are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ESTIMATED AND ACTUAL CONTENTS OF FLY ASH IN DIFFERENT PFC SAMPLES

Sample No.	Fly Ash Content, per cent Estimated (a)	Actual (b)	a—b, %
1.	8.38	5.0	3.38
2.	10.56	7.5	3.06
3.	12.74	10.0	2.74
4.	15.10	12.5	2.60
5.	17.38	15.0	2.38
6.	19.55	17.5	2.05
7.	21.38	20.0	1.38
8.	23.64	22.5	1.14
9.	26.08	25.0	1.08
10.	31.06	30.0	1.06

A comparison of the estimated values with actual contents of fly ash in different pfc samples shows that (i) the test overestimates by 1.06 to 3.38 per cent and (ii) the magnitude of overestimation is higher at lower contents of fly ash. The overestimation is considered to be due to the fact that neither portland cement and gypsum are fully soluble nor fly ash is fully insoluble in picric acid-methyl alcohol solution as shown by the data in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SOLUBILITY OF DIFFERENT MATERIALS IN PICRIC ACID—METHYL ALCOHOL SOLUTION

Material	Solubility, %
Portland cement	97.52
Gypsum	91.21
Delhi fly ash	9.14
Faridabad fly ash	7.76
Neyveli fly ash	4.12

Commercially produced pfc normally contains 20 per cent or higher amounts of fly ash. At these fly ash contents the overestimation is only 1.38 per cent or less. This is permissible. The test can therefore be used for quick estimation of fly ash content in pfc sold in the market.

Acknowledgement

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Physico-Chemical Studies of Quinoline and 8-Hydroxy Quinoline Complexes of Blue Perchromate

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COMPLEXES of the blue perchromate with different organic nitrogenous bases have been studied by different workers.¹⁻⁷ Magnetic measurements of red and blue perchromates have been done by Tjabbes⁸ and Klemm and Werth.⁹ Bhatnagar, Prakash and Hamid¹⁰ and Tomar, Singh and Singh¹¹ have measured the magnetic moments of the complexes of the blue perchromate. In the present communication quinoline and 8-hydroxy quinoline complexes of the blue perchromate have been studied. Chemical evidence has been supported by magnetic and I. R. Studies.

Experimental

Chemicals used were of A.R. Grade, Blue perchromate was prepared as described earlier.⁵ Wiede's method (loc. cit) was used for preparing complexes of quinoline and 8-hydroxy quinoline.

Quinoline Complex: To 50 ml. cold ethereal blue perchromate, excess of quinoline was added. Dark brown ppt. was obtained on keeping the mixture overnight. The ppt. was filtered, washed with cold ether (till the filtrate was colourless) and then dried in a desiccator.

8-hydroxy quinoline complex: To 50 ml. of cold and ethereal blue perchromate excess of 10% ethereal solution of 8-hydroxy quinoline was added. A green ppt. was obtained immediately. The ppt. was filtered and washed with ether till the filtrate was colourless. It was then dried in a desiccator.

Estimation of the elements: Chromium was estimated as Cr₂O₃ by igniting definite weights of the complexes in a silica crucible. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by combustion method, while the amount of oxygen was determined by difference. Results are recorded in Table 1.

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